

DRAGON BALL XENOVERSE 2

Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2 Review

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

GAME INFO

- **ORIGINAL TITLE:** *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* —ドラゴンボール ゼノバース 2—
- **DIRECTOR:** Yuka Kobayashi, Takeshi Sakamoto
- **PRODUCER:** Masahiro Kashino
- **DEVELOPER:** Dimps Corporation, QLOC —PC version—
- **PUBLISHER:** Bandai Namco Entertainment Inc
- **GENRE:** Fighting / Role-playing
- **PLATFORMS:** PlayStation 4, Xbox One, Microsoft Windows, Nintendo Switch
- **RELEASE DATE:** 28/10/2016 (PS4, Xbox One, PC) —Japan versions 02/11/2016
- **LAUNCH PRICE:** approx. £49.99 / €64.95 / \$59.99 (standard edition)

Official cover of the international version of *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2*

Be One with the Dragon Ball Universe

The studio Dimps returned for action only a year after releasing the original *Dragon Ball Xenoverse* on both previous-generation consoles (PlayStation 3 and Xbox 360) and PC, as well as on the newer PlayStation 4, Xbox One, and Steam platforms. The first title was a tremendous success, which quickly prompted the studio to begin work on its sequel, the current game.

This game aims to transport the player into Son Gokū’s world and that of his companions, without a doubt. With its strengths and weaknesses—which will be unpacked throughout this review—Dimps has delivered a game that, were it not so closely tied to the continuity of its predecessor and thus somewhat uninnovative, would offer an outstanding experience both in gameplay and atmosphere.

Players are given the option to create their own character and, using the main story as an excuse, take part in the most memorable battles of the *Dragon Ball* franchise, controlling “that lost friend” of Gokū and the gang who arrives to lend a hand and defeat the villains of the moment.

My Time Patroller, a Saiyan transformed into a Super Saiyan Level 3, facing Beerus—or Bills—the God of Destruction, alongside Piccolo, in a side mission.

Mechanics and Gameplay

The experience of the Dimps team is evident in every minute of gameplay. Indeed, it could hardly be otherwise from a team formed by former members of Capcom who created the original *Street Fighter*.

Since its foundation in 2000, the studio has contributed to a wide range of video games: platformers, such as the Sonic Advance series for the Game Boy Advance; role-playing games, like *Tales of the Tempest* for the Nintendo DS; and it also worked closely with Capcom on *Street Fighter IV*—being responsible as well for the version on the Nintendo 3DS handheld console—alongside the subsequent *Street Fighter V* of 2016, the last major *Street Fighter* title they worked on at the time of writing. They have also been involved in other anime- and manga-related video games, including titles based on *Saint Seiya*, *One Piece*, and *Bleach*.

Moreover, as the creators of the Budōkai series for the PlayStation 2—one of the most beloved fighting game franchises based on the *Dragon Ball* series—the expectations placed upon them have always been extremely high, which explains why any product related to Toriyama’s manga that they develop is judged so rigorously.

Xenoverse 2 may not satisfy enthusiasts of the Budōkai series in the same way those games did, but it is nonetheless a highly commendable proposition for the eighth generation of consoles and PC. It is worth noting that it is the first *Dragon Ball* video game, alongside its predecessor *Xenoverse* (2015), to appear on PC—if we disregard *Dragon Ball Online* (2010), which never officially left Asia.

We are not faced with a video game masterpiece, nor is it the best *Dragon Ball* game in existence, but it is certainly an excellent title.

Dragon Ball Xenoverse 2 is primarily a fighting game, with elements of role-playing and massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPG). From the first genre, it takes the influence that the core objective of the game is essentially to combat other characters.

From the second, it draws upon RPG elements that allow for character progression: levelling up, thereby increasing certain statistics; acquiring new equipment to modify these statistics; using items to, for example, restore a character's health; the possibility of employing various attacks and skills; and the ability to alter how a character fights according to personal preference.

Finally, from MMORPGs, it inherits the capacity to offer a “hub” where up to 300 people can coexist in the same room—linked to an online server—and interact with one another. Players can converse with other characters, challenge them to battles, and participate in missions together, regardless of whether the players behind those characters are on one's friends list.

Combat, a crucial aspect of any fighting game—and even more so in a title set in a series like *Dragon Ball*, where confrontations between protagonists and their foes carry significant narrative weight—is well crafted, even if it does not perfectly replicate the series' battles in the game in the way some fans have been anticipating for years.

The Time Patroller of *Xenoverse 2*, our personalised avatar, soaring over Conton City—the location that serves as our operational base in this game, providing access to all game modes, items, equipment, and abilities.

Our characters can block attacks, dodge, counterattack, fly freely across the stage, move at high speed...

All of this is achieved through very simple controls that respond well to the player—it is recommended to use a gamepad or joystick when playing on PC, such as Xbox 360 or Xbox One controllers, which the game will recognise instantly.

The camera generally adjusts appropriately, considering the amount of movement occurring on-screen, although occasionally it can behave annoyingly and disrupt combat, failing to position correctly and thus preventing us from avoiding attacks when surrounded by adversaries.

For combat, there are two types of attacks: strong and fast. Both can be chained together to create combos —sequences of consecutive hits. Players can execute a variety of attacks, even reaching over a hundred hits in a single combo if they know how to link them correctly. Grapples or throws can also be performed when an opponent attempts to defend or is left vulnerable.

Additionally, each character has a ranged attack thanks to ki waves —spiritual energy— that can be fired repeatedly by pressing the assigned button rapidly, or charged to perform different variants, such as a rapid burst in the style of Vegeta or Trunks, or a tracking sphere with delayed explosion effects, like those of Piccolo Daimaō Jr.

These abilities increase the potential for chaining long combos against opponents, leaving them vulnerable and preventing them from escaping to counterattack.

Players can also employ the Instant Transmission technique, for example, when a series of strikes sends an enemy into the air or onto the ground; this allows positioning behind them to continue attacking, thereby preventing their escape and increasing the damage inflicted. Furthermore, after launching an enemy, one can follow up with ki waves or a “Super Attack” or “Ultimate Attack” —high-powered special moves, such as Vegeta’s Final Flash or Son Gokū’s Super Kame Hame Ha— as finishing blows.

The combat and gameplay system is not as complex nor does it offer as much variety of combinations as found in titles such as Tekken, Soul Calibur, Street Fighter, or other *Dragon Ball* games like *Budōkai 3* or the Budōkai Tenkaichi series. However, with sufficient play and study, the player realises that there is significant potential and much to learn.

Victory is not achieved merely by repeatedly pressing the fast or strong attack buttons—a tactic that may succeed in the first story battles or early side missions— but requires knowledge of when and how to use available powers to prevent the opponent from easily dodging or countering them with their own techniques.

Moreover, the high difficulty posed by certain AI characters and/or specific missions, alongside the skill of players encountered online, compels continual improvement.

Although it may initially appear that constantly mashing attack buttons can secure victory —something that will occur in the first encounters with characters like Cell, C-18, Freezer, or Cooler— this is far from guaranteed. Difficulty escalates, and inexperienced players can be defeated without landing a single hit.

The sheer variety of techniques is noteworthy, with literally over a hundred distinct powers available, including special attacks, combos, evasive manoeuvres, enhancements, and transformations. Players can create characters capable of transforming into various forms of Super Saiyan —such as the classic version, Vegeta’s unique form, or the future forms of Trunks and Gohan— or utilise the Kaiō-ken technique, and wield powers such as Piccolo’s Makankōsappō or Ten Shin Han’s Kikōhō.

The game has improved mechanics for countering players who typically evade and bombard from a distance. For example, fewer consecutive ki shots are fired, allowing for counterattacks and approach, and a skill now enables a rapid dash toward an opponent, striking them if they attempt to escape, at the cost of some of the player's stamina.

Transformations have also been adjusted. In the first *Xenoverse*, activating Super Saiyan granted infinite ki, leading to rampant use of Ultimate Attacks online, preventing fair counterplay. *Xenoverse 2* rectifies this, preventing abuse such as an enemy executing twenty consecutive Super Kame Hame Has without limitation.

Now, while combat is slightly faster, chaining attacks, dodging, and responding to opponents is more intuitive, providing more enjoyable skirmishes once controls and timing are mastered. This creates moments of frustration when a combo seems to trap an enemy, yet they can escape, reposition, and retaliate —adding challenge and entertainment to battles.

Presentation and Atmosphere

Dimps employed Unreal Engine 4 for graphics, the Havok engine for physics, and the middleware YEBIS 2 for post-production effects. The combination is effective, with *Xenoverse 2* running at a near-constant 60 frames per second across all available platforms.

On PC, the game is relatively easy to run even on machines that are not especially powerful by current standards. Nevertheless, occasional crashes or desktop exits may occur in the Windows version —the Unreal Engine 4, like its fifth iteration, is known to exhibit such issues due to less optimisation compared to previous versions— though stability has improved through patches.

The technical aspect of *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* surpasses that of its predecessor, the first *Xenoverse*. The main city is larger —in this case, our protagonist interacts with other characters in Conton City, significantly bigger than Toki Toki City from *Xenoverse*, and includes small homage areas to classic *Dragon Ball* locations, such as Planet Namek or the Kame House.

Although the graphical leap is not dramatic, refinements in character brightness —overly exaggerated in the first game— are welcome.

Our character soaring over the Capsule Corporation area, home to Bulma's family, one of the locations where battles can take place in *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2*

Visuals and Presentation

The visual execution of the game by the studio is commendable. More than once, players may forget that they are observing 3D models of *Dragon Ball* characters and environments, and instead feel as if they are watching frames from the traditional animated series.

In this way, there are shots in the story mode that are reproduced to the smallest detail from the original *Dragon Ball Z* series or its films. For example, in the fight against Raditz, the animation matches exactly in angles, camera work, and timing with the classic series.

In summary, it is clear that Dimps employs enthusiasts of the original *Dragon Ball* animated series and manga in their offices. Models—even those from *Dragon Ball Super*, such as the “Super Saiyan Blue” transformations or characters like Beerus/Bills—appear as if designed and drawn in the 1990s, retaining the classic character proportions rather than the more stylised appearances seen in *Super*.

Traditional 2D animation sequences, produced by Toei Animation itself, are even incorporated at certain moments. Unfortunately, character animations are primarily notable in story mode, being rather limited during exploration of Conton City or in side and parallel missions, where NPCs interact in a mostly static manner—though flight, combat, attack, dodge, and transformation animations are meticulously crafted.

Players can create their own character—male or female—except for Namekians or the Frieza race, who are hermaphroditic or asexual, respectively. There are five races to choose from: Human, Saiyan, Namekian, Frieza's race, and Majin (Bū's species). Each race and gender has distinct statistics, and some abilities, transformations, and some equipment exclusive to each race. NPCs react differently depending on the protagonist's chosen species.

Players may visit Vegeta at Capsule Corporation to train and unlock the Super Saiyan transformation for Saiyan characters, or receive the “Purification” transformation from Bū, allowing them to become a “Small Bū” —similar to Bū prior to absorbing Great Kaiō Shin.

Game sequence animated by Toei Animation in which part of Conton City can be seen, populated by numerous Time Patrollers

The character can visually integrate seamlessly into Toriyama’s universe, aided by extensive customisation options for facial features, body types, hairstyles, and a wide variety of equipment —some inherited from original series characters, such as Master Roshi’s school gi or combat outfits from Frieza’s forces, as well as new equipment designed specifically for *Xenoverse* and *Xenoverse 2*, all respecting the franchise’s visual style.

Levels are spacious, permitting travel between different areas within the same stage where battles or missions occur. Locations from the series are faithfully recreated —it is particularly impressive to witness the Namek combat stage moments before its destruction by Frieza.

However, destructible elements within these environments are limited, considering that *Dragon Ball* characters can disintegrate entire planets or drastically alter terrain. For instance, a Kame Hame Ha striking the ground produces only a small crater, which quickly disappears.

Certain details are welcome, such as rocks levitating when a character charges energy or transforms —propelled by rising power or falling when the transformation is halted— or the ability to literally slam opponents into environmental elements, reminiscent of the original series.

One recurring shortfall —longstanding in *Dragon Ball* video games— is the absence of the irreplaceable original soundtrack composed by Shunsuke Kikuchi for the original *Dragon Ball* and *Dragon Ball Z* anime, which somewhat diminishes the atmosphere.

While the work of DJ and composer Steve Aoki is acceptable and generally complements the action, some tracks clash or feel unnecessary, such as Conton City’s theme and others. This can be remedied in the PC version using fan-created mods.

Aside from the soundtrack, the game’s sound design is faithful to the original series. Transforming into a Super Saiyan or launching a Genki-dama evokes the feeling of watching an episode of the animated series. Even subtle details, such as the characteristic stretching sound of Piccolo’s arms during attacks, or the unmistakable sound effects accompanying character teleportation, are present.

Regarding voice acting, the main limitation is the absence of the outstanding dubs produced for the Iberian Peninsula. Neither Basque, Catalan, nor Spanish versions are available; however, the English version is provided, alongside the opportunity to enjoy the iconic Japanese voices of Masako Nozawa (Gokū, Gohan, Goten, Turles, Bardock...), Ryūsei Nakao (Frieza), Toshio Furukawa (Piccolo), and much of the original series' cast.

Bills —also known as Beerus— in an animated sequence produced by Toei Animation specifically for this video game, voiced in the Japanese version by the same sei'yū who portrayed him in *Battle of Gods*, *Resurrection 'F'*, and *Dragon Ball Super: Kōichi Yamadera*

Moreover, the game includes subtitles in several languages such as English which, unfortunately, are not flawless. From time to time there are inconsistencies in names — for instance, Beerus may be referred to as either Beerus or Bills; or Krillin may appear as Klilin or Krilin depending on the translator in question, rather than consistently adopting one form.

There are also occasional Latin American usages for the Spanish version that may feel somewhat jarring to speakers of Peninsular Spanish as they are literal translations from English —for example, expressions such as “*apúrense*” (“hurry yourselves”) or “*te acabaré*” (“I will finish you off”) appearing in the subtitles.

Nevertheless, they are generally adequate and fulfil their function of helping players understand what is occurring on screen, particularly for those who do not speak Japanese.

Available Game Modes

Among the various modes available, the story mode is of course included, continuing the narrative established in *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse*. In this mode we assist Future Trunks in resolving various problems related to temporal distortions affecting the original history of *Dragon Ball*.

Throughout the story we receive assistance from the Supreme Kai of Time, Chronoa; the Elder Kai; and Trunks himself, and occasionally even from Son Gokū and other characters.

Characters such as Towa and Mira—who first appeared in *Dragon Ball Online*—also return. According to producer Masayuki Hirano, both characters were greatly appreciated by Toriyama, who was reportedly delighted that their stories were further developed.

Towa, as she appears in *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2*. She is no less diabolical than her brother Dabura, and once again seeks to make use of her power and knowledge in order to carry out her sinister plans of conquest.

Towa once again plans, as in *Xenoverse*, to manipulate the flow of time to her advantage, attempting to interfere with key moments in the history of *Dragon Ball*. In this instalment, in addition to the most important battles of the original *Dragon Ball Z* series, narrative arcs drawn from the *Dragon Ball Z* films are also included, such as that of Bardock, a character who can likewise be unlocked and controlled by the player.

Players will encounter both enemies and protagonists such as Bardock, Turles, Broly, and

Slug—who are also available as playable characters—as well as elements drawn from *Dragon Ball Super* and *Resurrection 'F'*.

Finally, missions set within the original Future Trunks arc are included. In this storyline, the future version of Son Gohan becomes Trunks's mentor after the deaths of all the other protagonists and supporting characters who were friends of Gokū—including Gokū himself—with the exception of Bulma.

The Future Trunks timeline also unlocks the possibility of a secret alternative ending for *Xenoverse 2*. I will not reveal it here so as not to spoil the experience for those who have not yet completed the game, but it will certainly satisfy fans of Trunks and Son Gohan.

Admittedly, the narrative functions primarily as a device to motivate the player to progress and confront increasingly powerful enemies, while contributing to the game's atmosphere. It is a very simple storyline—nothing comparable to productions such as *The Last of Us*, so expectations should remain modest. Nevertheless, its inclusion is welcome, even if it can become somewhat inconvenient to complete it in order to unlock many playable characters and stages.

This may prove frustrating for players who simply wish to launch the game, choose their favourite characters, and immediately begin fighting.

Trunks will recall, together with the players, one of the saddest and most moving scenes of his past: the loss of his mentor, Son Gohan, at the hands of the fearsome Androids created by Doctor Gero; an event that would become the catalyst for the personality of the brave Future Trunks we all know.

In addition, 100 parallel missions are included, allowing us both to relive great battles from *Dragon Ball*, *Dragon Ball GT*, and the *Dragon Ball* films, as well as to experience several “what if” scenarios —situations in which, for example, we may ally ourselves with Frieza in order to defeat Son Gokū on Namek, or join Vegeta, Nappa, and Raditz in order to overcome the protagonists of the series.

For these parallel missions, we may either use the character we have created ourselves or any of the fighters we have already unlocked—even selecting Cooler in a mission in which we must face Cooler himself. Some missions will be relatively easy, while others require defeating a large number of enemies, some of them possessing formidable difficulty—especially if we attempt them with a low-level character or mediocre abilities and attacks.

One curious feature is the constant interaction and dialogue between characters, a detail that is greatly appreciated. These interactions do not appear solely in story mode or in parallel missions, but in any battle we undertake—Mr Satan, for instance, will display great fear in his dialogue if he is losing, offering excuses for his poor performance, such as claiming that “his stomach hurts”, just as he would in the original series.

It is also noteworthy that each character seems to possess dialogue lines for practically every opponent they may face—Frieza will mock Krillin’s fighting ability if we pit them against one another, recalling that he killed him on Namek in the original series, and will show particular hatred towards Gokū, or disbelief and even fear when confronting Lord Beerus in battle.

Naturally, the classic local battle modes are included, as well as online matches —and it is here where we shall encounter genuine challenges in most cases, given the skill level of many players. The game also incorporates boss battle modes —such as encounters against Broly, or the Ōzaru forms (the giant ape transformations) of Saiyan characters like Vegeta or Nappa— in which up to six players may cooperate simultaneously to defeat them.

There is also an Endless mode, in which we must fight as many consecutive battles as possible without being defeated, as well as the option to play with equalised statistics — that is, characters will possess identical attributes when at the same level, meaning that victory will depend purely on player skill.

To this we may add the classic *Dragon Ball* video game feature, the Tournament mode —based on the Tenkaichi Budōkai from the series— as well as the training mode, where we can test abilities and experiment with different configurations of characters, skills, and equipment.

Another option available is the unlocking of various “masters”. For example, we may request the teachings of Son Gohan if we encounter him in Conton City, enabling us to learn the techniques he knows —such as the Masenkō.

When speaking with these masters — Yamcha, for instance, will even teach us a technique allowing us to play dead— we are given the opportunity to test their techniques in combat against them. This allows us to observe how the techniques function first-hand and unlock them for our character once the training session concludes. Furthermore, these masters may appear to assist us in the midst of battle —as illustrated earlier when Piccolo appeared to aid my Time Patroller during the fight against Beerus.

Our Time Patroller learns one of the techniques capable of destroying planets from Frieza himself (fortunately, the destruction was taking place in the Dragon Ball version of Hell, and not anywhere near Gokū and his friends).

With our personalised avatar we may also take part in various mini-games, such as “enduring” Master Roshi’s training —for example, Yamcha will throw stones bearing the “Turtle” or “Kame” symbol, just as the Turtle Hermit did in the original series, requiring us to search for them across the stage, much as Gokū and Krillin did when they were young and training under the old master.

We may even challenge the various forces of Frieza’s army in order to become members of it —which will lead us to confront Frieza himself, and even his brother Cooler, outside of story mode and the parallel missions. Alternatively, we may protect the chamber of the Grand Elder of Namek from enemy attacks, search for the Dragon Balls within battle stages, or even be challenged to fights while flying around Conton City and its surrounding areas —for example, Dodoria may challenge us to combat if we encounter him while flying.

As an additional feature, in several missions we may face other Time Patrollers—customisable characters similar to our own—adding further difficulty to those missions.

Despite all of this, the game can become repetitive—as is often the case with fighting games—since, regardless of the number of extra features available, the core activity ultimately revolves almost exclusively around fighting other opponents.

Nevertheless, the inclusion of all this additional content is greatly appreciated, even if some players may find it somewhat tedious should they simply wish to enter the game for a quick battle and nothing more.

Range of Stages and Characters

We shall visit locations such as Kami's Hyperbolic Time Chamber, West City, Capsule Corporation, and the World Martial Arts Tournament Stadium—Tenkaichi Budōkai—amounting to a total of 28 distinct stages, including several variations.

This instalment introduces characters not present in *Xenoverse*, such as Imperfect Cell, Nail, and Android 16, bringing the number of fighters available in addition to those already present in *Xenoverse* to seventeen. The roster continued to expand through downloadable content—by 2017, when this review was written, ten additional characters had already been added, including Hit, Vados, and Zamasu. Gokū Black from *Dragon Ball Super* also appears, although he is only available to players who pre-ordered the game—at least at the time this review was written, no alternative method of obtaining him had yet been confirmed.

The original roster of contenders exceeds seventy characters, including even several of Frieza's soldiers, the charismatic Mr Satan and his daughter Videl—Videl also appearing in her Great Saiyaman 2 costume—as well as Pan, in her appearance from *Dragon Ball GT*.

Naturally, it must be taken into account that nearly all characters possess multiple variations, both in terms of transformations and different costumes, as well as distinct sets of abilities and techniques for each version. For example, Son Gokū has around ten variants, while Son Gohan appears in several versions depending on the stage of life represented in the series, or whether we are referring to Future Son Gohan.

In some cases we encounter characters who are technically the same individual but are separated into distinct entries, while in other cases a single slot includes all available variations. Ten Shin Han, for instance, ranges from his classic appearance to his version from *Resurrection 'F'*, all within a single character slot.

To all these possibilities—which nevertheless do not surpass the immense roster variety of *Budōkai Tenkaichi 3*, which approached one hundred fighters without counting transformations or character variants—we must add the characters created by players themselves. These also possess different variations, since we may store several equipment, item, and skill sets, selectable as variations of our character, in the same way as the official *Dragon Ball* characters.

Finally, it is possible to import our save file from *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse*, allowing our customised Time Patroller —also known as the Future Warrior— to appear in this second instalment. The first Time Patroller plays a role in the story of this sequel —if the data is not imported, we may instead choose their appearance from several predetermined options— and doing so will also allow us to unlock a wide range of equipment and items previously obtained in the original *Xenoverse*.

The recreation of the environments and characters is the best seen to date in a Dragon Ball video game at a visual and technical level —although the environmental destruction seen in other Dragon Ball titles is somewhat missed. The blows can almost be “felt”, much as in the classic animation of the 1990s, something to which the excellent work of the game’s sound team greatly contributes.

***Xenoverse 2* pays the price of having been released too soon**

This is a detail that we cannot overlook throughout our entire playthrough.

Unfortunately, although *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* ultimately proves to be a nearly outstanding product as a fighting game —and particularly as a translation of the sensation of combat seen in the anime, OVAs, and films of *Dragon Ball Z*, *Dragon Ball GT*, and *Dragon Ball Super* into video game form— it nonetheless suffers from several shortcomings that remain constantly noticeable.

The first is that, however we choose to view it, *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* is essentially presented as little more than a “more and better” version of *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse*.

Although *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* is a new game, offering sufficient new content and clearly surpassing the original title in many respects, it still suffers from being overly conservative and from having been released only one year after the original instalment, *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse*. This inevitably leads one to wonder whether *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2* might have been released as an expansion for *Xenoverse*, or whether additional development time could have produced a title more clearly differentiated from the original, both conceptually and technically.

Had *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse* not existed beforehand, this sequel would appear far more original —indeed, it improves upon the first instalment in almost every respect— and it is precisely here that the game falters in terms of originality.

The second drawback is the regrettable absence of any attention paid to the earliest narrative arcs of the *Dragon Ball* manga —the story of Son Gokū's childhood and youth, his confrontation with Piccolo Daimaō and Piccolo Daimaō Jr., and so forth. Instead, characters and scenes appear only from the beginning of the *Dragon Ball Z* animated series onwards— that is, from the Saiyan saga forward.

Scores

- **Overall:** 74/100
- **Story:** 50/100
- **Graphics:** 95/100
- **Sound:** 80/100
- **Originality:** 50/100
- **Gameplay:** 95/100
- **Review Title:** Good

Conclusions

Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2 is a very respectable video game that reaches near excellence in many aspects, yet it suffers from being excessively continuist and from having been released too soon after its predecessor. For this reason, its originality cannot be rated highly.

It should also be borne in mind that, as a production based on a manga and anime franchise, the game is primarily aimed at enthusiasts of the series itself, *Dragon Ball*. Consequently, it may not satisfy those unfamiliar with the franchise to the same extent.

All things considered, it remains a solid fighting game, whose technical execution and design elements are almost impeccable. Among its strengths are its availability across multiple platforms and its various game modes, offering possibilities both for online play and for single-player experiences.

Sources

- **Text written by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
- **Images sourced from:** Official cover of *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2*; personal screenshots from *Dragon Ball: Xenoverse 2*, Steam version (PC)

Licence and original publication

- **Licence:** This article and its content are published under **CC BY 4.0**, which permits sharing and adapting the material provided that the source and author are credited
- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 9 March 2017 —Reseña de «Dragon Ball Xenoverse 2»—*
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*